

A Survey of Knowledge and Practices of Transfusion Medicine among Medical Doctors in Private Practice in Ibadan, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Comprehensive knowledge of blood transfusion practices among clinicians has an important role in provision of safe blood but continuous education and the academic rigor is not as versatile in private sector as in tertiary hospitals. The objective of this study is to evaluate the knowledge of clinicians in private practice in Ibadan on transfusion medicine. Eighty-one medical doctors from the 5 urban local government areas were enlisted in a multistage sampling technique. Self-administered questionnaires were employed and data analyzed using SPSS. Majority of clinicians were between the ages of 30-40 years (43.2%), had practiced for 0-5 years (42.0%) and prescribed blood transfusion at least once a month (44.4%). Male: female ratio was 4:1. The proportion of correct answers to the questions about age, minimum weight, Systolic Blood Pressure and Diastolic Blood pressure as criteria for selection of blood donor were as; 56.8%, 72.8 %, 71.6% and 81.5%, respectively. The proportion of correct answers to the questions on contraindications for the transfusion of platelet and cryoprecipitate were as; 54.3% and 9.9 %, respectively. The overall Knowledge score ranged from 22.0% to 93.0% (Mean= 49.0%; SD=37.7%). The mean knowledge score of indications and contraindications for transfusion of blood components are 79.2% and 34.2%, respectively. The study demonstrated significant gaps in knowledge of transfusion medicine. This can be closed by a more deliberate review of medical curricula, continuous medical education by professional groups and relevant stakeholders, as well as, a state-wide clinical audit of transfusion services.

Keywords: Ibadan, Medical doctors, Private Practice, Transfusion medicine

INTRODUCTION

Blood transfusion is a highly effective and potentially life-saving treatment option, as well as an essential procedure in modern medicine.¹ Clinicians' knowledge

about blood products and their preparation, storage, doses, demands and administration may have profound impact on patients' care and transfusion outcome. Wide variation in

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transfusion practice and inappropriate transfusion may jeopardize their safety.²

Blood is a scarce and precious commodity judging by perennial shortage of blood, hence the need for appropriate use of blood components. Blood wastages, inappropriate use and transfusion reactions will no doubt contribute to increased treatment cost and poor outcomes. Despite advancing technology in transfusion medicine, infectious and non-infectious complications of blood transfusion are still a major concern, especially in a developing nation like Nigeria. Practice of transfusion medicine and outcomes is heavily impacted by knowledge base and attitudes of practitioners. It is thus important to assess for gaps in knowledge and practices of clinical blood transfusing among ordering physicians. The main precaution for reduction of blood use and transfusion reaction is to make educational programmes for clinicians.³ Nevertheless, medical schools provide insufficient education about transfusion and previous studies have shown that knowledge of clinicians need to be improved.⁴

One of the key factors that determines the efficiency of any blood system is physician's education on transfusion medicine. It is important to obtain a baseline level of knowledge and identify the gaps in knowledge of clinicians in transfusion medicine.⁵ Many studies have been conducted in the developed country to assess knowledge and practice about blood transfusion among clinicians and paramedics.⁶ These studies have shown insufficient knowledge of physicians in transfusion medicine and the need to expand and improve transfusion medicine teaching.⁷ Poor knowledge of appropriate use of blood and its component can also lead to sub-optimal use and waste of such precious commodity. This gap in knowledge may endanger patient safety. Therefore, it is important to examine knowledge of physicians in transfusion medicine, identify significant knowledge gaps, and suggest strategies to minimize them. Therefore, this study aimed to determine the extent of knowledge of blood ordering physicians in private practice regarding transfusion medicine in Ibadan, South-Western Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a cross-sectional, inferential study using multistage sampling technique. Pre-study survey revealed that most clinics in the sub-urban Local Government Area were maternity clinics, with either no clinician and/or mostly practicing high risk blood transfusion. Thus, the study was limited to the 5 urban local governments in Oyo state. Consequently, the numbers of private hospitals to be enrolled in each of these urban local government was predetermined by applying stratified random sampling technique. Thereafter, the enrolled hospitals in each urban local government were selected from the Oyo state database using simple random sampling technique. A clinician per hospital, who met the inclusion criteria, was recruited into the study. Eight-one medical practitioners in private practice in urban part of Ibadan, southwestern Nigeria participated in this study. Only clinicians who worked solely in the private sector and resided in Ibadan were recruited. At the end of the survey, 28 clinicians were recruited from Ibadan North, 10 clinicians from Northeast, 8 clinicians from Ibadan Northwest, 6 clinicians from Ibadan Southeast and 29 clinicians from Ibadan Southwest. These gave a total of 81 clinicians.

The survey solicited information on age, sex, marital status, year of medical practice, year of graduation from medical university, name of their medical university, and specialty, previous education regarding transfusion medicine during medical course, sufficiency of education, and suggestions for improving the current knowledge regarding blood transfusion; experience regarding blood transfusion; blood donor selection criteria; appropriate storage of blood components; indication and contraindications to transfusion of whole blood and its components and immediate management of blood transfusion reactions.

Pilot test of the research material was tested previously for its content clarity, validity and reliability. Data entry and analysis were carried out using the Microsoft office Excel and IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 22.0 Armonk, NY: IBM Corp). Descriptive and

inferential statistics were used to express the data. Mean score of knowledge in each domain was obtained by dividing the correct score by the total number of questions in the category. One point was scored for every correct answer, 0 for any incorrect one. The Oyo State Research Ethics Review Committee, Department of Planning, Research and Statistics Division, Ministry of Health Secretariat, Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria approved the study (AD13/479/1497) and each participant signed an informed consent form.

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents

Participants (n=81)	n	%
Gender		
Female	15	18.5
Male	66	81.5
Age groups		
<30	17	21.0
30-40	35	43.2
40-50	9	11.1
>50	19	23.5
NA	1	1.2
Years of medical practice		
0-5yrs	34	42.0
6-10yrs	17	21.0
11-15yrs	9	11.1
>15yrs	20	24.7
NA	1	1.2

Eighty-one doctors participated in the study. Modal age range of the participants was 30-40 years; 81.5% of the participants were male, while 18.5% were females (Table 1). The average experience of participants was 6 - 10 years. Prior experience of prescribing blood and blood products was 90.1% among the doctors; 90.1% of doctors stated that they had received training regarding transfusion medicine in medical school, but among them 71.6 % found this to be inadequate. About forty-one percent (40.7%) of the doctors stated that additional training will be extremely useful while 13.3% felt that it would be of little or no use.

The total knowledge score was 27, and results were scaled to percentage and grouped. The descriptive statistics of the knowledge score is presented in Table 2. The mean overall knowledge score was 49.0% (SD = 37.7), and the range was wide (22% to 93%). Seventy two percent (72%) of doctors obtained a score ranging from 50% to 100%, with the highest frequency seen in the 60% to 69% range (n=25) (Figure 1).

More than 50% of the doctors (Figure 2) demonstrated good knowledge level for each blood donor selection criteria. Eighty-two percent (82%) of medical doctors knew the standard range of Diastolic Blood pressure (DBP) of a potential donor while only 56.8% knew the standard age range of blood donors. The mean score of participants on knowledge of blood donor selection criteria was 72.0% (SD = 17.0; range = 33.3 to 100.0%) (Table 2). Ninety-nine percent of doctors obtained a score ranging from 50% to 100%, with the highest frequency seen in the 70% to 100% range (Figure 1).

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the Performance of medical doctors to questionnaire

Statistics	Blood donor selection criteria	Indication for blood component therapy	Contraindications	Storage temperature	Overall knowledge score
Mean (%)	72.0	79.2	34.2	49.0	49.0
Std. Deviation (%)	17.0	26.4	31.6	37.7	37.7
Minimum (%)	33.3	14.5	9.4	12.9	22.0
Maximum (%)	100.0	88.3	79.8	97.1	93.0

The mean knowledge score on indication for transfusion of blood and components is 79.2% (Table 2). Least knowledge level was obtained from indications for the transfusion of washed pack cells with less than 50% knowing the correct answers (Figure 3). Lowest response rate was equally noted in this question, as 46% did not attempt to state an indication for its transfusion (Figure

3). However, most participants (91%) demonstrated excellent knowledge of the indication for the transfusion of whole blood (Figure 3). Still, the knowledge level on the indications for other blood components were well above average because over 70% respondents correctly stated indications for each of these components except for washed packed cells.

Figure 1: General and section by section knowledge score of clinicians in private practice within Ibadan on issues regarding transfusion medicine.

Figure 2: Knowledge on criteria for the selection of a potential blood donor.

Figure 3: Knowledge of subjects on indications of transfusion of blood components.

Figure 4: Knowledge on contraindication of transfusion of blood components.

The mean score of participants on contraindications for the transfusion of blood components was 34.2% (Table 2). This indicates that the knowledge of participants concerning contraindications for the transfusion of blood components is poor. Except for the contraindications for the transfusion of platelet where about 50% of participants gave correct responses (Figure 4), the

performance on the other two components were well below 50% with even as low as 10% on the contraindication for the transfusion of cryoprecipitate. Twenty percent of the participants did not attempt these questions at all.

Table 3: Performance of medical doctors to questionnaire compared to their socio-demographic characteristics.

		Overall Knowledge Score					Total	χ^2 (p-value)
		< 40 (%)	40-49 (%)	50-59 (%)	60-69 (%)	70-100 (%)		
Age	<30	0	5	3	6	3	17	39.931
	30-40	0	6	6	9	14	35	(-0.001)
	40-50	5	0	1	2	1	9	
	>50	3	3	1	8	4	19	
	not answered	1	0	0	0	0	1	
Total		9	14	11	25	22	81	
gender	female	1	3	4	4	3	15	3.18
	male	8	11	7	21	19	66	(-0.528)
Total		9	14	11	25	22	81	
Previous Training	Yes	6	11	9	25	22	73	26.237
	No	1	3	2	0	0	6	(-0.001)
	not answered	2	0	0	0	0	2	
Total		9	14	11	25	22	81	
Frequency of Transfusion	once a year	0	4	3	7	7	21	4.369
	once a month	3	9	4	12	8	36	(-0.416)
	once a week	1	0	1	1	2	5	
	more than once a week	5	1	3	5	5	19	
Total		9	14	11	25	22	81	
Adequacy of Training	Yes	6	10	8	16	18	58	14.628 (0.067)
	No	1	4	2	9	4	20	
	Not answered	2	0	1	0	0	3	
Total		9	14	11	25	22	81	

The perception of the doctors on management of transfusion reactions was surveyed. Their perception on the management of transfusion reactions are presented in Figure 5. 66.7%, 75.3% and 72.8% medical doctors, respectively, stated that blood transfusion should be discontinued immediately following mild, moderate and life-threatening transfusion reactions. Participants prescribed administration of antihistamine, antipyretics, hydrocortisone, and other steroids; infusion of normal saline and/or crystalloid; treatment of symptoms following close monitoring of vital signs; regrouping and crossmatching; checking for clerical errors; as well as giving oxygen.

The mean score of the clinicians on storage temperature for blood and some blood components was 49.0% (SD = 37.7) (Table 2); 65% of doctors obtained a score ranging from 50% to 100%, with the highest frequency seen in the 60% to 69% range (Figures 1). Approximately 78% of doctors stated the standard storage temperature range (1-6 °C) for whole blood. The pattern of response to questions regarding storage temperature for packed cell and platelets was similar, 58% of the participants stated the appropriate storage temperature range for each of these blood components.

Figure 5: Participants perception on the management of a) mild; b) moderate; and c) life-threatening transfusion reactions

The overall knowledge of participants differed significantly within age groups (Table 3). Clinicians between 30 to 40 years old performed better than other age groups ($\chi^2= 39.931$; $p<0.001$). Thirty-six percent of the clinicians within this age group scored above average. On the other hand, clinicians between the ages of 40 to 50 years had the worst performance because just 5% scored above average and fall within this age range. Additionally, statistically significant differences were also identified between participants' overall knowledge score and their previous training ($\chi^2= 26.237$; $p< 0.001$) (Table 3). Participants with previous training had higher score than those with none. In the former group, 67% clinicians scored above average while in the latter group, 2% clinicians scored above average.

DISCUSSION

One of the key points in evaluating the quality of any blood transfusion system is the level of knowledge of doctors.² Physician training plays an important role in managing blood use as human errors are involved in the risks associated with blood transfusion therapy.⁸ Meanwhile, several research studies have discovered that there is still considerable inappropriate use of blood products.⁹ Correlation between the physicians' knowledge, usage of blood components and the inappropriate use of blood products have been demonstrated.¹⁰ In fact, a definite correlation between morbidity/mortality rate and the blood transfusion was shown.¹¹ In this study, most of the participating doctors indicated that they had previous education on transfusion and perceived the previous education they had as being sufficient. This, however, contrast the results observed in previous studies.¹²⁻¹⁵ These authors indicated that participants believed that they did not receive sufficient education regarding transfusion medicine and because of this they felt less competent in transfusion medicine and were aware of their weaknesses in the care of patients. However, it is noteworthy that most previous studies enrolled only residents in internal medicine training

before they entered another specialty, unlike the present study, that included only clinicians from private hospitals. The participants in this study had good knowledge about some donor selection criteria such as age range, minimum hemoglobin, and body weight required. Similar finding was reported by Chauhan, *et al*,¹⁶ among medical students at a medical college in North India. Many previous studies¹⁷⁻¹⁸ were also in concordance with this present study results. In contrast, however, another study conducted by Manikadan, *et al*,¹⁹ among medical professionals of Tamil Nadu reported lower proportion of having correct knowledge about the age limit. Result in this study is also different to that previously found¹³. Blood transfusion safety begins with blood donor selection, which is designed to protect both donors and recipients' health²⁰ in order to improve recipient safety, blood donor selection is the cornerstone to reduce the risk of transfusion-transmitted infections.²⁰ The efficacy of blood donor selection in reducing the prevalence of HIV seropositive donors was confirmed in a study conducted in Senegal based on epidemiological data.²¹ It is recognized that there is a paucity of high-quality evidence on which to base decisions on blood donor selection.²² Only individuals in good health should be accepted as blood donors. Good health is difficult to define, but certain associated parameters may be established from a brief medical history, observation and simple medical test.²² Knowledge of physicians regarding indications for transfusion, dosage of blood and blood products has an important impact on the optimal use of blood and blood components.¹³ Knowledge level of participants on questions about the indication for washed pack cells and contraindications of transfusion of some blood components was relatively low (below 50%) compared to other questions. Generally, insufficient knowledge could be attributed to deficiency in orientation or training in various areas of blood transfusion.²³ Improved knowledge of transfusion medicine has been demonstrated to correlate with improved decision-making, resulting in better patient care.¹² More so, the low level of knowledge of the participants in this section may be because most doctors in Nigeria usually transfuse whole

blood more than they do for blood components²⁴ as blood components are not readily available. Patients rarely require all the components of whole blood, therefore transfusing only the portion required for a specific condition or disease improves safety, allows for good inventory and maximum use of a very scarce commodity.²⁴ Evidence for the use of blood component are enormous compared to whole blood in the western part of the world

The perception of participating doctors in this study on issues related to the management of transfusion reactions revealed good knowledge level. The result is different from what was observed in assessment of hematology trainee knowledge of transfusion medicine in some European countries.²⁵ Equally, this study differ from what was obtained by Arinsburg, *et al.*,⁶ where participants did worst on the transfusion reaction section with 7.8% of questions answered correctly. Many participants in this study indicated that transfusion should be immediately stopped when a transfusion reaction is suspected. In addition, they stated that intravenous line should be kept open using appropriate fluids (usually 0.9% saline). Signs and symptoms of specific transfusion reactions were not evaluated. Physician should be able to recognize signs and symptoms of acute haemolytic transfusion reaction and be able to intervene properly if any of these are noted.²³ In modern transfusion practice, acute haemolytic transfusion reaction is rare because of modern blood banking practices.²⁶ In the event of transfusion reaction, a clerical check be performed by examining the product bag and confirming the patient's identification.²⁷ The patient's vital signs should be monitored and recorded at 15-minute intervals. Bag, tubing and post-transfusion blood sample should be sent to the laboratory for further investigation. At the blood bank, further investigation and clerical check are generally carried out to rule out incompatibility. Specific symptom arising from transfusion reactions is generally helpful. Antihistamines and antipyretic, respectively, can be administered for a mild allergic and non-hemolytic febrile transfusion reaction.²⁷

This survey reveals that knowledge of participant on blood and blood component storage was averagely satisfactory. Appropriate storage of whole blood and whole blood component is essential. One of the reasons why good storage temperature is paramount is because of the ability of red cells and platelets continue to metabolise and undergo a range of physiochemical changes during storage. The changes are collectively referred to as the 'storage lesion'. Storage lesion ultimately affects the in vivo function and survival of transfused red cells and platelets and thus limits their shelf life. Intensive scientific knowledge and practices on haemotherapy-related protocols are essential.²⁸ Such knowledge may contribute to safe transfusion of the patients which help to prevent transmission of infectious diseases, as well as reduce the possibility of medical transfusion errors.

In this study, the mean score obtained by participants who indicated that they receive training during their medical education was significantly higher than other groups. Similarly, the studies amongst Brazilian medical residents¹⁵ and in Shiraz, Iran¹⁸ on transfusion medicine revealed that score obtained by the participants who received training was higher than the other groups. These studies were however carried out amongst medical residents in the respective area of study. More so, it was observed in this study that male doctors perform better than their female counterparts, but with no statistical significance. This contrast what was observed in Navi Mumbai²⁹ revealing equal knowledge score between male and female participants. It is, however, similar to study by Kasraian and Tavassoli¹⁸ who noted that the mean score of knowledge was higher in men, though, at statistically significant level.

CONCLUSION

Index study demonstrates significant gaps in knowledge of clinical blood transfusion among physicians in Ibadan, as well as associated determinants of transfusion knowledge such as age of the practitioners, and years of medical practice. More significant knowledge gaps were observed

in specific areas such as contraindications for blood transfusion compared to indications for transfusion and blood donation criteria. There is a need for revision of the medical curricula for a more deliberate instruction and learning in transfusion medicine. Medical professional groups and regulators should ensure continuous medical education in area of transfusion medicine. As well, regular audits of transfusion services and haemovigilance systems should be encouraged to provide continual data for assessment of local transfusion practices.

Conflict of Interest

The authors hereby declare that there is no known conflict of interest in this study.

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